

PROBLEMS OF REFEREEING IN SPORTS AT THE PRESENT STAGE OF SOCIETY DEVELOPMENT

Nishanbayevich Oribjon Madaminov

Teacher of the Department of sports games of the Faculty
of physical culture of Fergana State University.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7298441>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 26th October 2022
Accepted: 04th November 2022
Online: 07th November 2022

KEY WORDS

Sports referees, sports games, refereeing team, sports law, personal qualities of the referee, physical culture and sports

Competitions in various sports are essential in introducing preschool children, schoolchildren, students, as well as people of various age categories to regular physical education and sports [5]. The rapid development of modern sports, and in particular sports games, imposes a serious responsibility on sports referees. Problems with biased refereeing were recorded already in 1906 at the extraordinary Games in Athens [3]. The judges from the host country of the Olympics were very sympathetic to their weightlifters, so the Greek strongmen were credited with the weight taken, even if they could not hold the bar. Two years later, in London, British boxer Douglas won the middleweight title thanks to a judge who was his own father. The evolutionary development in football refereeing began with the fact that there was no referee on the field, he sat on the podium and closely followed everything that was happening on the field. As soon as the players had any misunderstanding, they ran to him and he immediately passed his verdict. In 1878 the

ABSTRACT

Sports referees have always been in the zone of increased attention from critics, although it is obvious that modern sport is unthinkable without them. An important point for the successful solution of the problem of raising the authority of sports should be considered the presence of good relationships between the refereeing team and the leadership of the teams.

referee entered the field for the first time and became the twenty-third participant of the match. It took another 13 long years when football referees had assistants, and the refereeing team began to consist of three people [1-3].

Sports games belong to sports with so-called conflict activities, for this reason, the skill of referees should be at the level of the skill of the players in order to enable the audience to see the maximum charm of the game with a minimum of injury [4,6-7]. By improving the quality of refereeing, the judges not only work to increase their authority, but also contribute to the main business - the growth of the skill of the players, raising interest in the sport among the masses and its popularization. The new law on sports undoubtedly refers a sports referee to the participants of a sports competition.

An important point for the successful solution of the problem of raising the authority of sports should be considered the presence of good relationships between the refereeing team and the leadership of

the teams. The personal qualities of the judges, their courage, objectivity, deep knowledge of the rules of the game and the methodology of judging, their tact, good manners not only become a decisive factor in increasing the entertainment of the competition, but also have a huge educational value for all parties involved in the competition (both playing teams, coaches, officials, and spectators) [6-7]. Sport needs referees who do not blindly follow the rules, but who have mastered their fundamental provisions, who think on the sports field, are creative and able to quickly and deeply analyze the most difficult situations created during the match.

Sports refereeing requires sufficient administrative distance from the main participants of the competition.

It should be emphasized that sports referees may bear special responsibility for poor-quality refereeing.

Bribery of participants and organizers of professional sports competitions and spectacular commercial contests), which established criminal liability for bribing a sports referee. With regard to the situation in our country, this means to systematize the work on the search, training, selection, retention and professional development of Russian judges and inspectors, which, ultimately, will allow – thanks to serious competition and the necessary rotation – to grow, establish and dominate true professionals. First of all, there are not enough judges to serve municipal, city, district, regional level competitions, school, "yard", children's, youth teams tournaments.

The development and complication of the subject composition of sports legal relations actualizes the scientific

understanding of the problem of the proper determination of the legal status of sports judges, taking into account foreign experience in this field, as well as the experience of international sports organizations directly managing the relevant sports.

The relevance of this issue is determined by other trends. Thus, some authors note that in the continuing development of the world of professional sports, sports referees who perform their functions within the framework of the largest events are increasingly responsible, and their decisions can influence not only the game itself, but also the commercial interests associated with it.

The analysis of the activity of sports judges allows us to identify the following specific features of the labor relations of sports judges: — subordination of a sports judge in his activities to the sports federation to the organizer of the competition or an independent organization of judges; as a consequence — the spread of the main feature of the labor relationship to them; — significant specificity of the sports result of a sports judge, i.e. the result of the work performed by a sports referee, the exercise of his powers and the exercise of his functions according to an employment contract: (a) the specific nature, content and structure of the sports result of a sports referee in professional sports; b) a specific sports result of a sports referee, which includes several elements: the objectivity of the resulting assessment of his sports results, as well as this assessment itself as a result of visual and intellectual assessments based on a comparison of the quality and other performance parameters of a professional athlete or sports team with the specified

parameters or with similar parameters of their rivals — others participating in this sports competition of professional athletes or sports teams; balanced and objective refereeing in strict accordance with the requirements of the rules of the sport and taking into account the interests of sport, in particular, a reasonable and optimal ratio of the number of punishments imposed for incorrect behavior of athletes and violations of the rules during a sports competition and the actual number of such acts (excluding obvious gross violations, which must be recorded and punished); the quality of the competition in terms of compliance with the rules of the sport and the rules of this competition (of this type or form), the provision of sports order during the competition; the trust of athletes and fans;

At the same time, in football, for example, as noted in the Strategy for the Development of Refereeing and Inspection in football for the period 2013-20204, the number of qualified referees for the period from 2019 to 2022 increased slightly (from 3,000 people to 4,000), which is clearly insufficient for the quality of numerous football competitions at all levels. According to statistical calculations, this indicator should have increased by 2.5 times.

An understanding of foreign experience of similar relations and issues is essential for developing appropriate approaches to solving the above-described problem and, in general, in the development of state policy in this sphere. 5 It should be noted that in relation to various sports, there are different types and categories of sports referees, which are designated by different terms, and in foreign legislation various terms are also used, which in general can

be translated into Russian as "judge". In order to avoid confusion (and since the study of various categories of judges, whose legal status is usually similar, was not included in the purpose of this work), we will continue to use mainly the term "sports judge".

The term "employee" is not suitable due to the fact that a sports referee does not always have an employment relationship with a sports organization, and the term "functionary" is more applicable to officials of such organizations with whom sports referees may not be bound by a long-term contractual relationship. Therefore, here we will use the term "official". A sports referee has a status similar to that of members of governing bodies of sports federations, as he is endowed with certain and very significant powers for the duration of a sports competition, and with the status of athletes and coaches, since he is a participant in a sports competition with similar working conditions. At the same time, sports referees enter into labor relations with sports organizations to a lesser extent, unlike professional athletes and coaches. The need to provide a clearer definition of the legal status of a sports referee is due to the need for more effective protection of his rights.

The legal status of a sports referee should also be determined in such a way as to ensure his authority for the participants of a sports competition. Sports functionaries play a very important role in the sports industry when conducting sports events, however, as a rule, they do not receive very high incomes like other participants of events when it comes to professional sports, and to a lesser extent become the objects of public attention.⁸ Nevertheless, it is worth noting that the practice of using

the image rights of sports referees by sports organizations takes place, including in some states it is regulated at the legislative level (which will be revealed later).

Sports referees should only take the necessary measures to ensure compliance with the rules of the competition, which include, for example, advising participants about prohibited techniques. At the same time, each situation is unique, and when resolving relevant disputes, the assessment of the behavior of a sports referee will be carried out in comparison with the behavior of a prudent and reasonable person with similar qualifications and experience. Sports officials cannot be held responsible for improper or irresponsible behavior of participants in a sports competition, and also, if their duties are properly performed, they cannot be held responsible for an injury to an athlete.

The status of sports referees in foreign legislation is defined rather vaguely, most issues related to ensuring the rights of these specialists in the field of sports are determined in accordance with the regulatory documents of sports organizations in which they carry out their professional activities, however, we can talk about some tendency to strengthen the protection of some basic rights of sports referees at the national level of legal regulation. It is impossible to talk about the existence of any general trends towards determining the legal status of a sports referee, as a rule, if it is regulated by legislation, it is only fragmentary.

Nevertheless, it is possible to identify some of the main existing approaches: — attribution of a sports referee to sports specialists (or another collective category of persons engaged in servicing sports

events, which does not include athletes, for example, to the so-called officials of sports competitions); — equating the status of a professional sports referee in certain cases with the status of a professional athlete or coach and extending the relevant provisions of labor legislation to the judge; — equating the status of a sports referee participating in significant sports competitions with the status of a top—level sports athlete and granting him the appropriate benefits and rights; — separating sports referees into a separate independent category of sports subjects and giving them a certain legal status different from the status of other subjects; - the absence in legislation of norms establishing the legal status of a sports judge or an arbitrator

When determining the legal status of a sports judge, it is necessary to take into account that, as noted earlier, a sports judge in different sports can be understood as different specialists with a different list of functions, as well as the fact that the specifics of the activity of a sports judge significantly depends not only on the sport, but also on whether this segment is professional sports, amateur sports, or sports of the highest achievements. There are approaches that define only the status, rights and procedure of professional sports judges who carry out their activities in professional sports, judges who carry out their activities only in amateur sports, as well as approaches that establish only the status of sports judges in some sports, such as, for example, boxing or football (and other team game sports).

This may be due to the specifics of these sports and dictated by the public interests of ensuring safety in sports, the need for a clearer definition of the special rights of a

sports referee (for example, the right to stop a competition if necessary) and the implementation of stricter control over the activities of such referees, establishing stricter requirements for them than it can potentially be implemented at the level of themselves. sports organizations that are not related to these interests.

Also note that in the legislation of different states, different (sometimes radically) points of view can be implemented on the question of whether a sports referee should be considered as a participant in labor relations. In the world, both at the legislative level in foreign countries and at the level of regulatory regulation of sports organizations, there is no consensus either on determining the legal status of a sports referee in general or on mandatory —

However, we note the following aspects that, taking into account the experience of foreign states and international sports organizations in this area, could potentially be effectively taken into account with the further development of the legislation of the Russian Federation in this area: — the establishment of a certain inviolability of sports referees in relation to actions carried out by them as part of the performance of their functions at sporting events; — establishing responsibility for the use of violence against a sports referee in connection with the performance of his functions; — equating the status of a sports referee as a subject of labor relations with the status of professional athletes and coaches.

References:

1. Болотин, А.Э. Педагогическая технология использования средств физической культуры для адаптации студентов к профессиональной деятельности / А.Э. Болотин, В.А. Щеголев, В.В. Бакаев // Научно-теоретический журнал «Теория и практика физической культуры». – 2014. - № 7 – С.16-20.
2. Болотин, А.Э. Показатели, определяющие высокую эффективность деятельности преподавательского состава кафедр физического воспитания / А.Э. Болотин, А.В. Караван // Научно-теоретический журнал
3. Xasanov, A. T., & Xankeldiyev, S. X. (2014). Research professional-applied physical training of students in the faculties of military education. *Europaische Fachhochschule*, (11), 57-59.
4. Хасанов, А. Т. (2017). СОЦИОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ В СИСТЕМЕ ПОДГОТОВКИ СТУДЕНТОВ ДОПРИЗЫВНОГО ВОЕННОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ. *Велес*, (7-2), 73-75.
5. Orifjon, M. (2021). NO ONE CAN MAKE THE COUNTRY FAMOUS IN SPORTS. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(12), 908-911.
6. Сидикова, Г. С. (2022). ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ЗДОРОВОГО ОБРАЗА ЖИЗНИ У ДЕТЕЙ СТАРШЕГО ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА. *Таълим ва Ривожланиш Таҳлили онлайн илмий журналы*, 2(1), 6-11.
7. Sidikova, G. S., & Ibrahimovich, T. A. (2021). FORMATION OF CHILDREN'S HEALTH CULTURE AS A SOCIAL AND PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM. *Conferencea*, 71-74.

8. Хасанов, А. (2016). METHODS ACCENTED CLASSES WITH STUDENTS OF THE SPECIALIZED FACULTY IN THE PERIOD OF MILITARY TRAINING. American Scientific Journal, (5), 62-64.
9. Islamov, I. A. (2021). Fundamentals of promotion of sports and competitions and physical training among school students. Current research journal of pedagogics, 2(06), 85-89.
10. Islomkhoja, I. (2021). STUDY OF STUDENT LEVELS OF MOVEMENT ACTIVITY AND INTEREST IN PHYSICAL TRAINING AND SPORTS TEACHER OF FACULTY OF PHYSICAL CULTURE. Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities, 1(1.5 Pedagogical sciences).
12. Sidikova, G. S., & Ibrahimovich, T. A. (2021). FORMATION OF CHILDREN'S HEALTH CULTURE AS A SOCIAL AND PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM. Conferencea, 71-74.
13. Sidikova, G. S., & Ibrahimovich, T. A. (2021). FORMATION OF CHILDREN'S HEALTH CULTURE AS A SOCIAL AND PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM. Conferencea, 71-74.
14. Nishanbayevich, M. O. (2022). Outdoor Games in The System of Physical Culture and Sports in Higher Education. Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies, 5, 18-20.
15. Tulanovich, Y. T., Madaminovich, D. E., & Baxodirovna, X. B. (2021). RHYTHMIC GYMNASTICS IN THE SYSTEM OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION. Innovative Technologica: Methodical Research Journal, 2(12), 25-29.
16. Hodjibayeva, I. V., & Ikromov, I. I. (2018). Features of free economic zones. Теория и практика современной науки, (1), 778-779.
17. Kayumovna, R. M. (2021). Wellness Swimming as a Part of the Physical Education of Students. European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630), 260-263.
18. Qayumovna, R. M. (2021). Examining and monitoring of the impact of hypo dynamic factors on the state of physical fitness in students. Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices, 3, 40-43.
19. Сиддиков, Ф. З. (2021). ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ АКЦЕНТИРОВАННОЙ МЕТОДИКИ НА ПОВЫШЕНИЕ УРОВНЯ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВЛЕННОСТИ ЮНЫХ БАСКЕТБОЛИСТОВ. In Актуальные проблемы совершенствования системы непрерывного физкультурного образования (pp. 272-277).
20. Tursinovich, K. A., Zoirovich, S. F., & Tavakkalovich, A. D. (2021). Innovations in improving the professional and practical physical training of students of the military faculty. Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities, 2, 31-34.
21. Mamatov, U. E. (2019). HISTORY AND DEVELOPMENT HISTORY OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION. Экономика и социум, (12), 78-79.

22. Karimov, D. K. (2022). THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN BODY TYPES IN THE SPORTS SPECIALIZATION OF YOUNG ACROBATS. Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities, 2(1.5 Pedagogical sciences).
23. Хасанов, А. Т., Юсупов, Т. Т., & Алломов, Э. И. (2020). ПОДГОТОВКА СПЕЦИАЛИСТОВ ФАКУЛЬТЕТА ВОЕННОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ К ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНО-ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ. European Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences, (1), 108-113.
24. Tursinovich, K. A., Mirzaakhmadovna, M. F., & Alijonovich, E. T. (2022). 'Topical issues of pre-university preparation of students in the field of physical culture and sports. Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies, 7, 253-255.
25. Азимов, А., Азимова, М., & Меликузиев, А. (2021). Разработка научных основ подготовки спортивного резерва. Общество и инновации, 2(8/S), 283-286.
26. Азимова, М. К., Азимов, А. М., Меликузиев, А. А., & Мирзакаримова, С. С. (2020). ФАКТОРЫ, ОПРЕДЕЛЯЮЩИЕ ЗДОРОВЬЕ ЧЕЛОВЕКА. Психология здоровья и болезни: клинико-психологический подход.,
27. journals, S. (2022, June 22). Organization of Physical Culture and Recreation Work with Preschool Children. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/t85qc>
28. Mamasoliyevich, S. S., Abdumalikovna, M. S., & Kholmatova, N. (2022). A Life Sacrificed in the Development of Social Life. Kresna Social Science and Humanities Research, 3, 152-156.
29. Tojimatovna, N. D. (2021). Means Of Shaping the Health and Healthy Lifestyle of University Student Girls. Texas Journal of Medical Science, 2, 1-3.
30. Abdumalikovna, M. S. (2021). BASIT KORIEV'S LIFE BECAME A MILESTONE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MUSICAL AND THEATRICAL EDUCATION. Conferencea, 52-54
31. Сидикова, Г. С. (2022). ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ЗДОРОВОГО ОБРАЗА ЖИЗНИ У ДЕТЕЙ СТАРШЕГО ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА. Таълим ва Ривожланиш Таҳлили онлайн илмий журналы, 2(1), 6-11.
32. Mamasoliyevich, S. S., Abdumalikovna, M. S., & Kholmatova, N. (2022). A Life Sacrificed in the Development of Social Life. Kresna Social Science and Humanities Research, 3, 152-156.
33. Ashurova, O. A. (2021). AESTHETIC EDUCATION AS A FACTOR OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF PRESCHOOL TEACHERS IN A PEDAGOGICAL UNIVERSITY. Theoretical & Applied Science, (5), 425-427.
36. Ashurova, O. (2021). Analysis of foreign experience on the development of eco-aesthetic culture of future preschool education specialists. Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research, 10(10), 1478-1484.
37. Ashurova, O. A. (2021). SOCIO-HISTORICAL TRADITIONS OF DEVELOPMENT OF ECOESTHETIC CULTURE OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL PROFESSIONALS. CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS, 2(05), 46-52.

38. Ashurova, O. (2021, December). THE IMPORTANCE OF AESTHETICITY OF ECOLOGICAL CONSCIOUSNESS AND CULTURE IN THE ACTIVITIES OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL PROFESSIONALS. In International Scientific and Current Research Conferences (pp. 88-90).
39. Anvarjonovna, A. O. (2021). Factors for the Development of Ecoesthetic Culture of Future Preschool Educational Professionals. European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements, 2(5), 162-164.
40. Anvarjonovna, A. O. (2021, December). Methodological Foundations for Development of Aesthetic Culture Teacher of Preschool Education. In INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH AND INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES (Vol. 2, pp. 254-258).
41. Anvarjonovna, A. O. (2021, December). Methodological Foundations for Development of Aesthetic Culture Teacher of Preschool Education. In INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH AND INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES (Vol. 2, pp. 254-258).
42. Anvarjonovna, A. O. (2021). AESTHETIC CULTURE OF THE EDUCATOR. In Interdisciplinary Conference of Young Scholars in Social Sciences (pp. 253-255).
43. Sidikova, G. S., & Ibrahimovich, T. A. (2021). FORMATION OF CHILDREN'S HEALTH CULTURE AS A SOCIAL AND PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM. Conferencea, 71-74.
44. Sidikova, G. S., & Ibrahimovich, T. A. (2021). FORMATION OF CHILDREN'S HEALTH CULTURE AS A SOCIAL AND PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM. Conferencea, 71-74.
45. Ashurali Ibragimovich Tuychiyev (2022). O'QUVCHILARDA INTIZOMIY KO'NIKMALARNI RIVOJLANTIRISH DOLZARB PEDAGOGIK MUAMMO SIFATIDA. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (2), 896-901.
46. Туйчиев, А. И. (2022). ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ РАЗВИТИЯ ДИСЦИПЛИНАРНЫХ НАВЫКОВ УЧАЩИХСЯ НА ОСНОВЕ ИГРОВЫХ СРЕДСТВ: уйчиев Ашурали Ибрагимович, Преподаватель Ферганского государственного университета. Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал, (2), 160-162.
47. journals, S. (2022, June 22). Organization of Physical Culture and Recreation Work with Preschool Children. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/t85qc>
48. Abdumalikovna, M. S. (2021). BASIT KORIEV'S LIFE BECAME A MILESTONE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MUSICAL AND THEATRICAL EDUCATION. Conferencea, 52-54
49. Xaydaraliev, K. (2019). THE EXPERIENCE OF CHARGES AND FACULTIES USING THE NEW MODERN INFORMATION DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM IN TRAINING. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol, 7(6).
50. Хайдаралиев, Х. Х. (2019). МОТИВАЦИЯ ВЫБОРА ПРОФЕССИИ КАК ПРОЯВЛЕНИЕ ПАТРИОТИЗМА СОВРЕМЕННЫХ СТУДЕНТОВ. In EUROPEAN RESEARCH: INNOVATION IN SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND TECHNOLOGY (pp. 50-52).

51. Tojimatovna, N. D. (2021). Means Of Shaping the Health and Healthy Lifestyle of University Student Girls. *Texas Journal of Medical Science*, 2, 1-3.
- Orifjon, M. (2021). NO ONE CAN MAKE THE COUNTRY FAMOUS IN SPORTS. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(12), 908-911.
52. Tursinovich, H. A., Ibrokhimovich, A. E., & Tavakkalovich, A. D. (2022). Features of the interdependence of indicators of physical status of students of I-IV stages of military education faculties. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 7, 58-61.
53. Хасанов, А. Т., Юсупов, Т. Т., & Алломов, Э. И. (2020). ПОДГОТОВКА СПЕЦИАЛИСТОВ ФАКУЛЬТЕТА ВОЕННОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ К ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНО-ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ. *European Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, (1), 108-113.
54. Сидикова, Г. С. (2022). ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ЗДОРОВОГО ОБРАЗА ЖИЗНИ У ДЕТЕЙ СТАРШЕГО ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА. *Таълим ва Ривожланиш Таҳлили онлайн илмий журнали*, 2(1), 6-11.
55. Sidikova, G. S., & Ibrahimovich, T. A. (2021). FORMATION OF CHILDREN'S HEALTH CULTURE AS A SOCIAL AND PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM. *Conferencea*, 71-74.
56. Sidikova, G. S., & Ibrahimovich, T. A. (2021). FORMATION OF CHILDREN'S HEALTH CULTURE AS A SOCIAL AND PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM. *Conferencea*, 71-74.
57. Sidikova, G. S., & Ibrahimovich, T. A. (2021). FORMATION OF CHILDREN'S HEALTH CULTURE AS A SOCIAL AND PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM. *Conferencea*, 71-74.
58. journals, S. (2022, June 22). Organization of Physical Culture and Recreation Work with Preschool Children. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/t85qc>
59. Ashurali Ibragimovich Tuychiyev (2022). O'QUVCHILARDA INTIZOMIY KO'NIKMALARNI RIVOJLANTIRISH DOLZARB PEDAGOGIK MUAMMO SIFATIDA. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3 (2), 896-901.
60. Madaminov Oribjon Nishanbayevich. (2022). Outdoor Games in The System of Physical Culture and Sports in Higher Education. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 5, 18-20. Retrieved from <https://zienjournals.com/index.php/tjm/article/view/718>
61. Tursinovich, H. A., Ibrokhimovich, A. E., & Tavakkalovich, A. D. (2022). Features of the interdependence of indicators of physical status of students of I-IV stages of military education faculties. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 7, 58-61.
62. Robilova, S. M., & Patidinov, K. D. (2022). Physical training of handball and its comparative analysis practitioners. *Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities*, 12(4), 173-177.
63. Туйчиев, А. И., & Сидикова, Г. С. (2022). ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ ФИЗКУЛЬТУРНО-ОЗДОРОВИТЕЛЬНОЙ РАБОТЫ С ДЕТЬМИ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА. *JURNALI*, 178.